

STRUCTURED LEARNING APPROACH (SLA) MODIFICATION TO IMPROVE SHARING SKILLS OF AT-RISK STUDENTS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

Asieline Wahyu Tri Ardyanti¹,
Immanuel Hitipeuw,
M. Ramli

Universitas Negeri Malang, Indonesia

Abstract:

This study aims to determine the effect of Structured Learning Approach (SLA) modification to increase social skills in primary school for at-risk students. This study used a single subject design with multiple baselines across subject models. The subjects of this study are five (5) at-risk elementary school students in 3rd grade. The data collection instrument consists of the format of recording the frequency of social skills (sharing), social skills identification instruments, shared knowledge, evaluation of sharing skills, observation of social sharing skills, and treatment instruments in the form of guidebooks. The results showed that SLA modification can improve the social skills of sharing, that is, the children's target of baseline average 4.0 increased to 8.0, the target child AD average baseline 2.7 increased to 7.0; Target child ZD average baseline 2.3 increased to 6.7; The target child AR average baseline 3.0 increased to 6.3; and the target child baseline average increased to 5.3.

Keywords: Structured Learning Approach modification, sharing skills, students at risk

1. Introduction

The condition of multicultural society in Indonesia can lead to the emergence of various problems. This issue currently occurs which everyone can easily identify. What happens recently is a political feud, child abuse, poverty, malnutrition and a lack of humanitarian tolerance to respect the rights of others. The problem has resulted in

¹ Correspondence: email asieline.wahyu.ta@gmail.com

Indonesia as a nation at risk, resulting in a number of rising at risk children. The diversity of the Indonesian people, including ethnicity, race, culture, language, religion, and social status should be a potential that can be utilized for the progress of the Indonesian. According to UNICEF data in 2016, 2.5 million Indonesian children cannot pursue further education as many as 600 thousand primary school children (SD) and 1.9 million Junior High School (<https://www.unicef.org/indonesia/id/education.html>).

Numerous experts come up with a various definition and interpretation of risk. In general, at-risk children are considered as troublemakers, lazy children, caring for attention, selfish, and sometimes lying (Appelstein, 1988). At-risk children are also considered as children who are not graduating properly, lacking the necessary skills and confidence to work and establish a relationship with others (Sagor & Cox, 2004). Morris (2000) says that children at risk are individuals who are unlikely to be able to finish his or her school (drop out).

The future of a nation depends on the quality of its human resources and the ability of its learners to master the science and technology including at-risk students. It can be realized through education in the family, education in the community and education in schools.

School as one environment where every child can learn to socialize and can imitate positive behavior. By establishing a positive relationship between parents and children as well as teachers and students, it will be able to help create a good social environment, since it is essential to establish a close relationship and trust from at the very beginning (Pajares, 2012).

Social skills are the ability of individuals to show appropriate behavior in certain situations while performing a social task; behaviors that can be taught, studied, can be changed by behavior modification techniques and shown in various situations; Constructs related to other domains, namely social interaction, prosocial skills, and socio-cognitive skills (Vaughn, et al, 2001; Gresham, et al., 2001; Meaden & Monda-Amaya, 2008).

Social skills for children are essential for his or her success and adaptation in the school environment in which the child is located. When a child has good skills, it will affect his or her life, academic, and self-esteem. If the child lacks social skills, the child has the potential to experience rejection from peers, behavior problems, and low academic achievement. Several experts state that the formation of a person's behavior and emotions begins as a child (Goleman, 1996).

Based on the results of research and study of the phenomenon that occurred in the field, it can be concluded that students at-risk in elementary school require SLA (Structured Learning Approach) modification consisting of 5 components: direct

instruction, modeling, role playing, performance feedback, and, transfer of training maintenance (Arnold P. Goldstein, Robert P. Sprafkin, N. Jane Gershaw, and Paul Klein, 1976) in order to improve their social skills. If this activity is not taught earlier, particularly in elementary school, students at-risk will be increasingly ignored and avoided from friends and the environment. In addition, it will make at-risk student will get worse, anxious, very secretive and even frustration and will make them can be categorized as a child with special requirement since they possess settled negative behavior.

2. Method

The research subjects of this study are at risk students which were determined based on (1) social skills identification tools, (2) at risk students identification, (3) documentation of report cards, and (4) interviews with teachers. The subjects were the third year students of State School Polehan 5, consisting of twenty-five (25) students, and obtained five (5) students as research subjects.

The participation of teachers in the research setting was (1) together with the researcher determined the students who will be the subject of the research, (2) the class teacher and the researcher prepared the teaching of social skills to be achieved that is integrated in the learning, (3) and served as the observer in the data collection.

2.1 Behavior Target and Measurement

Target behavior is a sharing skill; this social skill refers to the concept suggested by Seven & Yoldas (2007). While measurement of target behavior was using the frequency of social skills is filled by researchers, teachers, and observers. As for social skills identification instruments, it was filled by researchers, teachers, and observers. For shared knowledge it was filled by students, evaluation of shared skills was filled by students; observation of shared social skills was filled by researchers, teachers, and observers.

The guidebooks and Materials, materials and materials prepared by researchers were validated by experts (expert judgment). The experimental design of this study employed single subject design with multiple baselines across subject's model with AB-A 'design (Barlow & Hersen, 1984; Creswell, 2012). Phase A is baseline and phase B is an intervention using SLA modification, while An' is maintenance.

3. Findings and Discussion

Figure 1 (a) shows the children's sharing skills of RK targets at baseline conditions conducted by three sessions tend to be stable with a mean of 4.00 level. Hence, immediate intervention was given. After three interventions were applied, sharing skills increased with the mean of the 8.00 level. On 3-session maintenance conditions, sharing skills decreased with the mean level of 7.00. If the level of change seen after the intervention, by looking at the mean level of baseline conditions and maintenance conditions obtained the difference of 3.00 means that the implementation of interventions can improve the sharing skill of student RK.

Figure 1(a): Sharing Skills of RK Target

Figure 1 (b) shows children's IR-sharing skills at baseline conditions conducted by 3 sessions and tend to be stable with a mean of 2.00 level thus immediate intervention was given. After 3 interventions were applied, sharing skills increased with the mean level of 6.00. On 3-session maintenance condition, sharing skill decreased with a mean of level 5.33. If the level of change seen after the intervention, by looking at the mean level of baseline conditions and maintenance conditions obtained the difference of 3.33 means the implementation of interventions can improve the sharing skill of student IR.

Figure 1(b): Sharing Skills of IR Target

Figure 1 (c) shows the ZD target child sharing skills at baseline conditions conducted by 3 sessions and tend to be stable with the mean level of 2.33 thus immediate intervention was given. After 3 interventions were applied, sharing skills increased with the mean level of 6.67. On 3-session maintenance conditions, sharing skills decreased with the mean level of 6.00. If we look at the level of change after the intervention, by looking at the mean level of the baseline condition and maintenance condition, the difference of 2.67 means that the implementation of the intervention can improve sharing skills of ZD.

Figure 1(c): Sharing Skills of ZD Target

Figure 1 (d) shows children's AR sharing skills at baseline conditions conducted by 3 sessions which tend to be stable with a mean of 3.00 level thus direct intervention was given. After 3 interventions were applied, sharing skills increased with the mean level

of 7.33. On 3-session maintenance condition, sharing skill decreased with mean level of 6.67. If the level of change seen after the intervention, by looking at the mean level of baseline conditions and maintenance conditions obtained the difference of 3.67 means that the implementation of interventions can improve the sharing skill of student AR.

Figure 1(d): Sharing Skills of AR Target

Figure 1 (e) shows the children's target sharing skills in baseline conditions conducted by 3 sessions which tend to be stable with mean level 2.67 thus direct intervention was given. After 3 interventions were applied, sharing skills increased with the mean level of 7.00. On 3-session maintenance condition, sharing skill decreased with mean level of 6.33. If the level of change seen after the intervention, by looking at the mean level of baseline conditions and maintenance conditions obtained the difference of 3.83 means which indicate that the implementation of interventions can improve the sharing skill of student AD.

Figure 1(e): Sharing Skills of AD Target

The following Table 1 presents the results of the target students' evaluation of the skills shared with Knowledge and Skills measurements.

Table 1: Evaluation Results on Students Knowledge and Skill on Sharing

Item	Knowledge					Skill				
	RK	IR	ZD	AR	AD	RK	IR	ZD	AR	AD
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	3	4
2	1	1	1	0	0	1	2	4	3	4
3	1	0	1	1	0	4	3	2	4	4
4	1	1	1	1	1	4	2	3	1	3
5	1	0	1	1	1	1	3	4	3	4
6	1	1	1	1	1	4	2	1	4	1
7	1	1	0	0	1	3	3	2	3	4
8	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	3	1	4
9	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	3	1	3
10	1	1	1	1	1	4	3	4	4	4
Score	10	8	9	8	8	26	25	29	27	35
Category	Very understand	Skilled	Skilled	Skilled	Skilled	Very skilled				

The results of knowledge sharing evaluation by target children RK obtained a score of 10 and included in the category Very understand, the target child IR obtained score 8 and included in the category Very understand, as well as ZD who obtained score 9, AR who obtained score 8, and AD who obtained score 8 which are considered as very understand.

While the results of evaluation of sharing skills by target children of RK obtained score 26, IR obtained score 25, ZD obtained score 29, AR obtained score 30 who are considered as skilled, and AD obtained a score of 35 to be included in the Highly Skilled category.

3. Conclusion

The use of SLA modifications is effective for improving social sharing skills for at-risk elementary school students. The five subjects showed an increase in sharing behavior, in order of RK, AD, ZD, AR, and IR. Thus, the implementation of SLA modification effectively improves the social skills of sharing individually or in groups at risk students. Teachers in the classroom play an important role in using SLA modifications. Teachers are required to ensure SLA modifications work well and simultaneously teach social skills for all students. In the learning process, students can experience a fun

learning experience, therefore, willingness, enthusiasm and behavior change behavior will be getting better.

References

1. Barlow, D. H. & Hersen, M. 1984. *Single Case Experimental Design: Strategies for Studying Behavior Change*. New York: Pergamon Press.
2. Creswell, J. 2012. *Educational Research Planning, Conducting, Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research Fourth Edition*. Boston: Pearson Education, Inc.
3. Gresham, F. M., Cook, C. R., & Crews, S. D. 2004. Social Skills Training for Children Youth with Emotional and Behavioral Disorders: Validity Considerations and Future Directions. *Behavioral Disorders*, 30 (1): 32-46.
4. Westwood, P. 2004. *Learning and Learning Difficulties: A Handbook for Teacher*. Victoria: Australian Council for Educational Research Press.
5. Alberto, P. A. & Troutman A.C. (1990) *Applied Behavior Analysis for Teacher* (Third Edition). Melbourne; Merrill Publishing Company.
6. Ali, M.2010. *Metodologi dan Aplikasi Riset Pendidikan*. Bandung: Cendikia Utama.
7. Allen, J. M. (Ed.). (1998). *School Counseling New perspectives & practices*. Greensboro, NC: ERIC/CASS Publications.
8. American School Counselor Association. (1999). *Position Statement: Special needs of students*. Alexandria, VA: Author
9. Arumugam, N., Thayalan, X., Kaur, K. & Muthusamy, C. (2013). It takes two tango: Academic environment and social skills. *Asian Social Science*, 9(4), 123-128. Doi:10.5539/ass.v9np123
10. Asher, S. R., & Hymel, S. (1981). *Children's social competence in peer relations: Sociometric and behavioral assessment*. In J. D. Wine & M. D.
11. Baker, S. B. (2000). *School counseling for the twenty-first century*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill.
12. Barr, J. A. 1958. *The Elementary Teacher Guidance*. New York: Hery Holt and Company.
13. Blankeship, C. & Cilly, M. S. 1981. *Mainstreaming students with learning and behavior problem, techniques for the classroom teacher*. New York: Holl, Rinehart, and Winson.
14. Barlow, D. H. & Hersen, M. 1984. *Single Case Experimental Designs: Strategies for Studying Behavior Change*. New York: Pergamon Press.

15. Creswell, J. 2012. *Educational Research Planning, Conducting, Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research* Fourth Edition. Boston: Pearson Education, Inc.
16. Gresham, F. M., Cook, C. R., & Crews, S. D. 2004. Social Skills Training for Children Youth with Emotional and Behavioral Disorders: Validity Considerations and Future Directions. *Behavioral Disorders*, 30 (1): 32-46.
17. Bandura, A. 1977. *Social Learning Theory*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
18. Bandura, A. 1986. *Social foundation of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Upper Sadle River, N. J.: Prentice Hall.
19. Belmont, J. M. 1989. Cognitive strategic learning: the socio instructional approach. *American Psychologist*, 44, 142-148.
20. Bergen, J. R. 1977. *Behavior Consultation Columbus*, OH: Merrill
21. Berk, L. 2001. *Development through the lifespan (2nd ed)*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
22. Blankeship, L & Lilly, M. S. 1981. *Mainstreaming Student Will Learning and Behavior Problems techniques for the classroom teacher*. New York: Holl, Rinehart, and Winson
23. Bremer, C. D. & Smith, J. Teaching Social Skills. *National Center on Secondary Education and Transition*, 3(1): 1-15.
24. Brown, W., Odom, S., & Buysee V. 2002. Assessment of Preschool Children's Peer related Social Competence. *Assessment for Effective Intervention*, 27 (4): 61-71
25. Burnham, J. J., & Jackson, C. M. (2000). School counselor roles: Discrepancies between actual practice and existing models. *Professional School Counseling*, 4, 41-50.
26. Borg, W. R. dan Gall, M. D. 2007. *Educational Research, an Introduction*. Fourth Edition. New York: Logman Inc
27. Cartledge, G., Milgurn, J. F. 1980. *Teaching Social Skills to Children*. New York: Pergamon Press.
28. Cartledge, G, Milgurn, J. F. (1983). Social Skills Assessment and Teaching in the Schools. *Advances in School Psychology*, 3, 175-235.
29. Campbell, C. A., & Dahir, C. A. (1997). The national standards for school counseling programs. Alexandria, VA: ASCA.
30. Chen, X. & Kaufman, P. (1997). "Risk and resilience: The effects of dropping out of school." Paper presented at the American Association of Educational Research (AERA), Chicago, Ill. [On-line]. Available: <http://nces.ed.gov/pubs>.
31. Cook, B. G. & Cameron, D. L. 2010. Inclusive Teachers' Concern and Rejection toward Their Students: Investigating the Validity of Ratings and Comparing

- Student Groups. Hammill Institute on Disabilities Remedial and Special Education, 31(2): 67-76
32. Cole, M. 1991. Conclusion. In L. Resnick, J. Levine, S. Teasley (Eds.), *Perspectives on socially shared cognition* (pp. 398-417). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
33. Creswell, J. 2012. *Educational Research Planning, Conducting, Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research Fourth Edition*. Boston: Pearson Education, Inc.
34. Clickeman, M.S. 2007. *Social Competence in Children*. Michigan. Springer Science Business Media
35. Deck, M., Scarborough, J. L., Sferrazza, M. S., & Estill, D. M. (1999). Serving students with disabilities: Perspectives of three school counselors. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 34, 150-155.
36. Detjen, E. W. & Mary, F. D. 1963 *Elementary School Guidance*. New York: Mc Graw-Hill Book Company, Inc.
37. De Vries, R. 1977. *Piaget's social theory*. *Educational researcher*, 26(2), 4-18
38. Donmoyer, R. & Kos, R. 1993. *At Risk Students: Portraits, Policies, Programs, and Practices*. State University of New York Press, Albany.
39. Dryfoos, J. 1990. *Adolescents at risk Prevalence and Prevention*. New York: Morrill
40. Dunn, N. A. & Baker, S. B. (2002). Readiness to serve students with disabilities: A survey of elementary school counselors. *Professional School Counseling*, 5, 277-284.
41. Education for All Handicapped Children Act of 1975, 20 U.S.C. 1400 et seq. Education Service Center VI. (2002). Demographic data analysis and information for school districts. Huntsville, TX.
42. Education Service Center VI. (2004). *The other yellow pages: 2004-2005 regional directory and school calendar*. Huntsville, TX.
43. Enggen, P & Kaucak, D. 2004. *Educational Psychology Windows Classrooms, International Edition*. New Jersey: Person Education Inc.
44. Erford, B. T. (2003). *Transforming the school counseling profession*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill.
45. Gardner, H. 1991. *The Unschooled Mind: How Children Think and How School Should*. New York: Basic Books.
46. Gardner, H. 1993. *Frame Mind: The Theory of Multiple Bits of Intelligence*. New York: Basic Books

47. Goleman, D. 1996. *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*. New York: Basic Books.
48. Gresham, F. M., & Elliott, S. N. (1984). Assessment and classification of children's social skills: A review of methods and issues. *School Psychology Review*, 13, 292-301.
49. Gresham, F. M., & Lemanek, K. L. (1983). Social skills: A review of cognitive behavioral
50. Training procedures with children. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 4, 239-261.
51. Gresham, F. M. & Elliot, S. N. (1990). *The Social Skills Rating System* American Guidance Service, Circle Pines, MN.
52. Gresham, F. M., Cook, C. R., & Crews, S. D. 2004. Social Training for Children and Youth with Emotional and Behavior Disorders: Validity Considerations and Future Directions. *Behavioral Disorders*, 30: 32-46.
53. Gresham, F. M., Sugai, G. & Horner, R. H. 2001. Interpreting Outcomes of Social Skills Training for Students with High-incidence Disabilities. *Exceptional Children*, 67 (3): 331-334.
54. Gibson, R. (1990). Teachers' perceptions of high school counseling and guidance programs: Then and now. *The School Counselor*, 37, 248-255.
55. Goodlad, J. 1984. *A Place Called School*. New York: Mc Graw-Hill.
56. Gysbers, N. & Henderson, P. (1997). *Comprehensive guidance programs that work - II*. Greensboro, NC: US Department of Education.
57. Harper, L., Rochelle & Fox, L 2009. "You Got It" Teaching Social and Emotional Skills *Journal of the National Association for the Educational of Young Children*.
58. Havighurst, R. J. Tanpa Tahun. *Human Development And Education*, (disadur oleh Moh. Kasiram, M. Sc. 1985) Surabaya: Penerbit Sinar Wijaya.
59. Hill, S. & Hill, T. 1993. *The Collaborative Classroom: A Guide to Cooperative Learning*. Victoria: Australia: Eleanor Curtain Publishing.
60. Hitipeuw, I., 2005. *Penanganan Masalah Siswa oleh Guru Melalui Direct Behavioral Consultation*. Disertasi Tidak Diterbitkan. Malang: Pascasarjana Universitas Negeri Malang.
61. Honig, A., & Wittmer, D. (1996). *Helping children become more prosocial: Ideas for classrooms, families, schools, and communities*. *Young Children*, 51(2), 62-70.
62. Hughes, J. N., & Sullivan, K.A. (1988). Outcome assessment in social skills training with children. *Journal of School Psychology*, 26, 167-183.
63. Hurlock, W. B. 1990. *Developmental Psychology: A Life Span Approach*, Fifth Edition. McGraw Hill Inc.

64. Individuals with Disabilities Education Act Amendments of 1997, 20 U.S.C. 1400 et seq.
65. Dobson, J., C. & Baure, G., L. 1990. *Children At Risk: what you need to know to protect your family*. Wheaton, Illinois: Tyndale House Publishers.
66. Jawa Pos, Jumat, 27 Maret 2015, hal 35. "Dua Siswa SD Setubuhi Teman".
67. Julia Segal. (2009). Pengantar Umum Psikoanalisis Sigmund Freud (terjemahan, cet 2) Pustaka Pelajar Yogyakarta.
68. Johnson, D. W. (1950). *Reaching Out*. Englewood Clifft, NJ: Prentice-Hall
69. Johnson, D. W & Johnson R.T. 2009. *Learning Together and Alone: Cooperative Competitive and Individualistic*. Third Edition Englewood Cliffs. NJ: Prentice Hall
70. Joyce, B. & Weil, M. 1996. *Models of Teaching* (5thed) Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon.
71. Joice, B. & Weil, M. (1980). *Model of Teaching*. Englewood Clifft, NJ: Prentice Hall.
72. Lawson C. 2000. *Social Skills and School*, dalam Cohen, L (Ed) 2000 *Raise Your Childs Social IQ: Stepping Stones to People Skills For Kids*. Silver Springs, MD: Advantage Books.
73. Levin, J. & Nola, J. F. 1996. *Principles of Classroom Management* (2nded). Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
74. Malecki, C. K. & Elliot, S.N. (2002). Children's social behaviors as predictors of academic achievement: A longitudinal analysis. *School Psychology Quartely*, 7 (1), 1-23.
75. Marlina. 2008. *Dinamika Penerimaan Teman Sebaya Pada Siswa Berkesulitan Belajar di Sekolah Inklusif*. *Jurnal Pembelajaran*, 30(2): 1-10
76. Marlina. 2013. *Penerapan Peer Mediated Intervention untuk Meningkatkan Keterampilan Sosial Pada Anak Berkesulitan Belajar di Sekolah Dasar Inklusif*.
77. Merrell, K. W., Merz, J. M., Johnson, E. R., & Rig, E. N. (1992). Social competence of students with mild handicaps and low achievement: A comparative study. *School Psychology Review*, 21, 125-137.
78. Merrell, K. W., Sanders, D. E., & Poppinga, M. R. (1993). Teacher ratings of student's social behavior as a predictor of special education status: Discriminant validity of the school social behavior scales. *Journal of Psychoeducational Assessment*, 11, 220-231.
79. Milsom, A. S. (2002). Students with disabilities: School counselor involvement and preparation. *Professional School Counseling*, 5, 331-338.

80. Noell, G. H. 1996. New Direction in Behavioral Consultation School Psychology Quarterly, II (3), 187-188.
81. Nowicki, E. A. 2003. A Meta Analysis of the Social Competence of Children with Learning Disabilities Compared to Classmates of Low and Average to High Achievement. Learning Disabilities Quarterly, 26(1): 1-61.
82. Ogbu, J. 1999. The significance of minority status. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association, Montreal, Canada.
83. O'Shaughnessy, T., Lane, K. L, Gresham, F. M., & Beebe-Frankenbeger, M. E. (2002). Students with or at-risk for learning and emotional behavior disorders: An integrated system of prevention and intervention. In K.L Lane, F.M. Gresham, & T. E., O'Shaughnessy (Eds.), Interventions for Children with or at Risk for Emotional and Behavioral Disorders (pp 3-17). Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
84. Pajares (2002). Overview of social cognitive theory and self-efficacy. Diakses tanggal 26 Maret 2015, dari <http://emory.edu/EDUCATION/mfp/eff.html>.
85. Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 19 Tahun 2005 tentang standar Pendidikan Nasional
86. Permendiknas Nomor 70 Tahun 2009: Tentang Pendidikan Inklusif Bagi Peserta Didik yang Memiliki Kelainan dan Memiliki Potensi Kecerdasan dan/atau Bakat Istimewa.
87. Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia. Nomor 111 Tahun 2014. https://mustafatope.files.wordpress.com/2014/11/permendikbud_tahun2014_nomor111.pdf
88. Pintrich, P. & Schunk, D. 2002. Motivation in education: Theory, research, and application (2nded.). Upper Sdale River, N.J: Prentice Hall.
89. Quinn, M. M., Kavale, K. A., Mathur, S. R., Rutherford, R. B., & Forness, S. R. (1999). A meta-analysis of social skill interventions for students with emotional or behavioral disorders. Journal of Emotional and Behavioral Disorders, 7(1), 54-64.
90. Quinn, M., Osher, D., Warger, C., Hanley, T., Bader, B., Tate, R., & Hoffman, C. (2000). *Educational strategies for children with emotional and behavioral problems*. Retrieved November 27, 2006, from the Center for Effective Collaboration and Practice Web site: http://cecp.air.org/aft_nea.pdf
91. Rashid, T. 2010. Development of Social Skills among Children at Elementary Level. *Bulletin of Educational & Research*. Vol 32, No I, pg 69-78.
92. Roueche, J. E. & Roueche, S. D. (1993). *Between a rock and a hard place*. Washington, DC: Community College Press.

93. Ruffalo, S. L., & Elliott, S. N. (1997). Teachers and Parent rating of children social skills A closer look at cross-informant agreement through an item analysis protocol. *School Psychology Review*, 26, 489-502.
94. Samanci, O. (2010). Teacher views on social skills development in primary school students. *Journal of Education*, 131(1), 147-157.
95. Santoso, S. 2000. Statistik Non parametrik. Jakarta: Elex Media
96. Santrock, J. W. 2002. Life Spain Development: Perkembangan masa Hidup. Jakarta. Erlangga.
97. Santrock, J. W. 2009. Psikologi Pendidikan (educational Psychology) Edisi 3Buku 1. Jakarta: Salemba Humanika.
98. Sainato, D., & Carta, J. (1992). *Classroom influences on the development of social competence in young children with disabilities*. In W.H. Brown, S.L. Odom, & S.R. McConnell (Eds.), *Social competence in young children with disabilities* (pp. 93-109). Baltimore, MD: Paul H. Brookes.
99. Schunk, D. 2000. Learning theories (3rd.ed). Upper Sdale River, N.J: Prentice Hall.
100. Schneiders, A. (1964). *Personal Adjustment and Mental Health*. New York: Rinehart & Winston
101. Seven, S. & Yoldas, C. (2007). *Sinif Ogretmeni Adaylarinin Sosyal Beceri Duzeylerinin Incelenmesi (Investigation of Social Skill Level of Prospective Classroom Teachers)*. Yuzuncu Yil Universitesi, Egitim Fakultesi Dergisi. Haziran 2007. Cilt:IV, Say 1:I, 1-18.
102. Sugiyono. 2009. Metode Penelitian Pendidikan, Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung : Alfa Beta
103. Staub, D. & Peck, C. A. 1994/1995. What are the Outcomes for Nondisabled Student?. *Educational Leadership*. 52. 4
104. Sunanto, J., Takeuchi, K. & Nakata, H. 2005. Pengantar Penelitian dengan Subyek Tunggal. CRISED: University of Tsukuba dan Upi Bandung.
105. Suryabrata, S.2010. Psikologi Pendidikan. Jakarta: Rajawali Press.
106. Slavin, Robert E.1995. Educational Cooperative Learning. Boston. Allyn and Bacon Publishers.
107. Slavin, Robert E. 1997. Educational Psychologir: Theory and Practice Fourth Edition. Allyn and Bacon
108. Stahl, R. J. 1994. Cooperative Learning in Social StudiS; A Handbook for teacher. United States of America; Addison Wesley Publishing Company.
109. Swastika, I. 2008. Program Bimbingan Untuk Mengembangkan Keterampilan Sosial Anak Berbakat Akademik. Tesis. Bandung : Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia.

110. Undang-undang Republik Indonesia nomor 20 tahun 2003 tentang Sistem Pendidikan Nasional.
111. Vaughn, S., Elbaum, B & Boardman, A.G. 2001. The Social Functioning of Students with Learning Disabilities: Implication for Inclusion. *Exceptionality*, 9 (1 & 2): 47-65.
112. Walker, H. M., &Severson, H. (2002). Developmental prevention of at-risk outcomes for vulnerable and antisocial children and youth. In K. L. Lane, F. M., Gresham, & T. E., O'Shaughnessy (Eds) *Interventions for Children with or at Risk for Emotional and Behavioral Disorders*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
113. Walker, H. M. (1983). *The ACCESS program: Adolescent curriculum for communication and effective social skills: Student study guide*. Austin, TX: Pro-Ed
114. Wentzel. 1991. Relations between Social Competence and Academic Achievement in Early Adolescence *Child Development* 62.3.1066-1078
115. Widyawati, F. 2008 Meningkatkan Keterampilan Sosial Siswa Terisolir di Sekolah Dasar dengan Permainan Tradisional. Tesis. Bandung : Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia.
116. Wong, B. Y. L. 2004. *Learning About Learning Disabilities*. Third edition. Canada: Elsevier Academic Press.
117. Zins, J., Weissbert, R., Wang, M., & Walberg, H. (2004). *Building academic success on social and emotional learning: What does the research say?* New York: Teachers College Press.
118. Zirpoli, T., & Melloy, K. (1997). *Behavior management: Applications for teachers and partners* (2nd ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall
119. http://www.researchgate.net/publication/254347165_SelfRegulation_and_Learning-Related_Social_Skills_Intervention_Ideas_for_Elementary_School_Students

Asieline Wahyu Tri Ardyanti, Imanuel Hitipeuw, M. Ramli
STRUCTURED LEARNING APPROACH (SLA) MODIFICATION TO IMPROVE SHARING SKILLS OF
AT-RISK STUDENTS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).